

The leverage effects of the Covid-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war on the stock markets of emerging countries

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Abstract

This study examines the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and Russian invasion of Ukraine on the stock markets of emerging countries such as Brazil, India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia, using the asymmetric GJR-GARCH model. The sample period runs from February 26, 2020 to May 5, 2023, divided into two sub-periods: the COVID-19 period and the Russia-Ukraine war period. The results of the study show that there was persistent volatility on these markets. In addition, the results obtained indicate that the leverage effect is significant in all the stock markets analyzed, confirming that bad news, such as the pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war, are risk determinants for the economy, has a greater impact on the conditional variance of returns than good news. It was also found that the Brazilian market was more affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, while the Indian, Saudi and Indonesian markets were more affected by Russian invasion of Ukraine. The results have important implications for international investors in terms of portfolio management and minimizing investment risks in the face of events such as pandemics and war.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, GJR-GARCH, asymmetry, Russia-Ukraine war, persistence, volatility.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, a new pandemic reported in Wuhan, China, known as the new coronavirus (COVID-19), with a specific capacity for person-to-person transmission, has spread around the world. Due to the transmission of the COVID-19 pandemic, all countries have taken measures to lock down their businesses and markets, and people are forced to stay at home. Employment has been severely affected, leading to a rise in the unemployment rate, industrial production has begun to fall sharply, damaging economic growth in emerging and developed countries alike, and tourism and travel sales have been drastically curtailed. In addition, stock markets around the world saw their prices fall.

Due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, stock market investors were faced with a high degree of financial uncertainty. Ngwakwe (2020) revealed that the Dow Jones Industrial Average recorded a significant reduction in average share value over the COVID-19 period. The S&P 500 and Euronext 100 indices showed a non-significant difference in average share price during the pandemic. Liu et al (2020) studied the stock markets of Japan, Korea, Singapore, the USA, Germany, Italy and the UK to assess the short-term impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The European stock markets are being affected by the conflict between Ukraine and Russia, as the main imports from Russia and Ukraine are being reduced. However, the impact of this war on the mining, construction and manufacturing sectors is greater than on the transportation and utilities sectors.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war on stock market performance and volatility in different regions has been the main topic of several recent studies, such as Gherghina et al. (2021) and Greta and Julius

(2021), who focused on the effects of COVID-19, and others, such as Ahmed and Mariya (2022), Boubaker et al. (2022) and Reza and Hassan (2023), who analyzed the impact of the recent Russian invasion of Ukraine and its global financial repercussions.

This study builds on the observations of Wang and Wu (2018), who recognized that investors are not only concerned with volatility, but also with asymmetric volatilities, to see if stock market reactions to "good" and "bad" news are different. The study therefore uses the asymmetric GJR-GARCH model to investigate asymmetric volatility transmissions between markets, an important factor in stock pricing, risk management, trading strategies and the benefits of diversification.

The aim of this article is to analyze the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war on the performance and volatility of stock market indices in four selected emerging countries. These indices are the Ibovespa (Brazil), the SENSEX (India), the Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia) and the IDX Composite (Indonesia).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Stock markets were hit by both the COVID-19 pandemic and the outbreak of war between Russia and Ukraine. Uncertainty in the financial world increased, and the confidence and expectations of stock market participants were compromised.

Several studies have examined the severe effects of the COVID-19 crisis on different stock markets, sectors and industries. Rashmi et al (2020) analyzed the impact of the pandemic on the performance and volatility of the stock market indices of the top 10 countries according to their GDP by applying the GARCH model (1,1). The results showed that the COVID-19 crisis had a significant impact and increased stock market volatility during the pandemic period.

Gherghina et al (2021) studied the Romanian stock market and examined the volatility of the BET (Bucharest Exchange Trading) index on stocks traded on the BSE (Bucharest Stock Exchange) between January 2020 and April 2021 using the GARCH (1,1) model. The results revealed that the volatility of Romanian equities increased as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Sansa (2020), in his study, found a positive impact of COVID-19 on the values of the US Dow Jones and Chinese Shanghai stock indices during the period from March 1 to March 25, 2020. Al-Awadhi et al. (2020) observed in their research on the impact of COVID-19 on the Chinese stock market, covering the period from January 10 to March 16, 2020, that in general, the increase in the total number of confirmed cases and the total number of death cases caused by COVID-19 has significant negative effects on stock performance.

Ftiti et al (2021) analyzed the volatility of the Shanghai stock market between December 31, 2019 and April 7, 2020. The authors found that the pandemic crisis led to higher stock market volatility and lower liquidity levels.

Bora and Basistha (2021) compare the Indian stock market at the start of the COVID-19 period and after the COVID-19 period, using the GARCH model to capture index volatility. The authors reveal that the coronavirus pandemic had a negative impact on the Indian stock market, where volatility was high. In addition, the study carried out a comparative analysis of stock market returns during the pre-COVID-19 period and during the COVID-19 period. The results show that the Indian stock market experienced volatility during the pandemic period. Comparing the results with those of the pre-COVID-19 period, they found that index profitability is higher in the pre-COVID-19 period than during COVID-19.

Nieto and Gonzalo (2020), analyzing the Spanish stock market from January 3 to April 29, 2020, showed that the COVID-19 pandemic significantly decreased the price performance of the IBEX 35 stock index and increased volatility. Greta and Julius (2021) studied the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic crisis on the stock markets of Italy and Spain, two of the most affected European countries, from March to August 2020. The results showed that the stock market's response to the pandemic depended on the country and the period studied.

O'Donnell et al (2021) analyzed stock market indices in China, Italy, Spain, the UK and the US to the growth in the total number of COVID-19 cases, covering the period between January 10 and the end of June 2020. They found that all indices, with the exception of the Chinese index, suffered a significant negative shock. Implied volatility, represented by investor sentiment, also had an important impact on index variations in general.

Khan et al (2020) studied the impact of COVID-19 on various stock market indices, namely the USA, China, the UK, South Korea and other countries, from April 9, 2019 to April 3, 2020. However, there were no reactions in the early stages of the pandemic. Curiously, the Shanghai Composite Index was affected by the pandemic but recovered very

quickly in the longer event window, mainly due to the immediate measures taken by the government to contain the spread of the virus.

Ozkan (2021) analyzed the effect of COVID-19 on stock market performance in six developed countries (USA, Spain, UK, Italy, France and Germany). The results showed abnormal returns during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Shehzad et al (2020) studied the impact of the 2007 financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic on returns and volatility in the Chinese, Japanese, US, Italian and German stock markets from June 30, 2007 to April 7, 2020. The results show higher volatility during the COVID-19 period, particularly in the US and EU markets, while average returns were negative overall. However, the US and Japan were the hardest hit.

Yousfi et al (2021) used daily data from January 5, 2011 to September 21, 2020, covering the periods before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, for the Chinese and US stock markets. The authors examined the asymmetric effects of shocks on the basis of correlations between the two markets and found evidence of contagion during the COVID-19 period.

Reza and Hassan (2023) analyzed the impact of the war between Russia and Ukraine on 83 countries between February 23 and March 23, 2022. The results showed that the decline in the value of stock market indices in response to the war was more pronounced in countries with stronger trade links (exports and imports), i.e. the impact was mitigated in countries with greater trade openness.

Marwan et al (2023) analyzed the impact of the Russia-Ukraine war and COVID-19 in 25 countries (G7 + rest of EU + rest of world) on stock market price volatility. The authors used data over a 6-month window, 3 months before and after specific expiration dates, March 9, 2020 for COVID-19 and February 24, 2022 for the war. The results showed greater volatility due to both events, although the impact of the pandemic was more pronounced.

Najaf et al (2023) checked the impact of Russia invasion of Ukraine on the performance of the Russian and Ukrainian stock markets in the period from January 1 to February 24, 2022. The results showed that the war led to higher volatility and lower performance of stock indices on both markets. However, the Russian market appears to have suffered a greater decline, mainly due to the actual economic sanctions imposed by the USA and its allies.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

3.1 Methodology

In this study, the analysis is carried out using various statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics, unit root tests, the ARCH effect test and the GJR-GARCH model.

Descriptive statistics include mean and median as measures of central tendency, and standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis as measures of variability. To confirm the normal distribution of yields, the Jarque-Bera (1987) test is applied. Time charts of daily stock index returns are used to provide a better picture. The returns of all stock market indices can be calculated using the natural logarithmic difference approach with the following formula:

$$r_t = \ln(P_t) - \ln(P_{t-1}).$$

Where r_t is the market index return, P_t is the closing price of the index on day t and P_{t-1} is the closing price of the index on the previous day (t-1).

The unit root test is used to check the stationarity of a data series. A time series is considered stationary if a change in time does not lead to a change in the shape of the distribution. If the series is stationary, this means that the mean, variance and autocorrelation structure do not change over a given period. Consequently, the ADF (Augmented Dickey-Fuller) (1979) and KPSS (1992) tests are applied. The former tests for the presence of a unit root as a null hypothesis, while KPSS tests for trend stationarity and has the absence of a unit root as a null hypothesis.

The ARCH-LM test, described by Engle (1982), is used to check the heteroscedasticity of residuals in order to detect the presence of the ARCH effect.

3.1.1 Asymmetric GJR-GARCH model

Engle (1982) proposed the first model to deal with conditional variance in financial series, called ARCH (Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity), i.e. conditional variance corresponds to an autoregressive model on the square of the errors. Bollerslev (1986) extended the work of Engle (1982) and developed the GARCH (Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity) model, which incorporates the conditional variance observed in the past into the ARCH model. Although the GARCH model captures volatility clusters, it does not detect the asymmetry of their distribution. For this reason, models have been developed to incorporate asymmetry issues. One of the first asymmetric models is EGARCH (Exponential GARCH), proposed by Nelson (1991). Glosten, Jagannathan and Runkle (1993), Ding, Granger

and Engle (1993) and Zakoian (1994) developed the GJR-GARCH, APARCH and TARCH (Threshold ARCH) models respectively.

This study uses the asymmetric GJR-GARCH model, which detects volatility asymmetry and tests the impact of higher volatility on "bad news" versus "good news".

Conditional mean equation

$$y_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t$$

Conditional variance equation

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_i u_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \sigma_{t-j}^2 + \gamma_1 u_{t-1}^2 d_{t-1}$$

Where σ^2 denotes conditional variance; ω , α and β are constant parameters; u_{t-1}^2 lagged quadratic residuals; d_{t-1} binary variable. The positive coefficient of asymmetry (γ) exists for leverage, meaning that negative shocks will have a greater impact on conditional volatility than positive shocks of the same magnitude, while the negative value of γ indicates the opposite.

3.1.2 Error distribution

For the GJR-GARCH model, the Gaussian (normal), Student t and Generalised Error Distribution (GED) distributions will be fitted, described below by the log-likelihood function.

Normal distribution (Gaussian)

$$L_{normal} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^n [\ln(2\pi) + \ln(\sigma_t^2) + \varepsilon_t^2]$$

Student t distribution

$$L_{student-t} = \ln \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{\nu+1}{2} \right) \right] - \ln \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{\nu}{2} \right) \right] - 0,5 \ln[\pi(\nu-2)] \\ - 0,5 \sum_{t=1}^n \left[\ln \sigma_t^2 + (1+\nu) \ln \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon_t^2}{\nu-2} \right) \right]$$

Where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function, ν corresponds to the degrees of freedom. It is $\nu > 2$, $\nu \rightarrow \infty$, if the student t distribution converges to a normal distribution.

GED (generalized error distribution)

$$L_{GED} = \sum_{t=1}^n \left[\ln(\nu / \lambda_\nu) - 0,5 \left| \frac{\varepsilon_t}{\lambda_\nu} \right|^\nu - (1+\nu^{-1}) \ln(2) - \ln \Gamma(1/\nu) - 0,5 \ln(\sigma_t^2) \right]$$

Where ν is the degree of freedom and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function, and

$$\lambda_\nu \equiv \sqrt{\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{\nu}\right) 2^{(-2/\nu)}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{\nu}\right)}}$$

This distribution generalizes the normal distribution and can have lighter ($k > 2$) or heavier ($k < 2$) tails than the standard normal ($N(0,1)$) and if $k = 2$ we get the normal distribution.

After making the necessary adjustments, it selects the best model on the basis of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) proposed by Akaike (1974).

3.1.3 Data

In this study, information was obtained from daily closing data on www.investing.com for emerging market indices, including Brazil (Ibovespa), India (SENSEX), Saudi Arabia (Athex Composite) and Indonesia (IDX Composite). The analysis period runs from February 26, 2020 to May 5, 2023. This period was chosen to include the COVID-19 pandemic (February 26, 2020 to May 05, 2023) and the Russia-Ukraine war (February 24, 2022 to May 05, 2023). The period considered for this study will enable us to understand the performance of stock markets in the selected emerging countries following the crises.

4. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This study adopts an empirical approach to examine the reaction of stock markets in selected emerging countries to the main events of COVID-19 and Russia's invasion of Ukraine, as well as to investigate the role of volatility asymmetry and capture the leverage of incidents and events on stock indices.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for daily share prices during the periods when the Covid-19 pandemic and Russia invasion of Ukraine affected the four emerging country stock markets studied. In Panel A - Covid-19, we observe that Brazilian share prices are the most volatile, as revealed by the standard deviation of 0.01923, while Saudi Arabia is the least volatile, with a standard deviation of 0.01120.

Skewness values are generally negative for all markets during the pandemic. Stock market kurtosis values are higher than those expected in a normal distribution, indicating a leptokurtic distribution for the entire sample period. In general, kurtosis values are high, indicating thicker tails during the pandemic. The Jarque-Bera test values further confirm that the daily yield series are not normally distributed, i.e. all p- values are 0.0000.

In Panel B - Russia-Ukraine War, the Brazilian stock market (Ibovespa) shows a strong deviation from the average share price, with a coefficient of variation of 29.21%. The Indonesian stock market, on the other hand, is the least volatile, as evidenced by a standard deviation of 0.00803. Jarque-Bera statistics show that not all stock prices are normally distributed during the Covid-19 pandemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war.

Table 1 - Descriptive statistics

Indicators	Ibovespa (Brazil)	SENSEX (India)	Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia)	IDX Composite (Indonesia)
Panel A - Pandemic Covid-19 (February 26, 2020 - May 5, 2023)				
Average	0,0000608	0,00055	0,00046	0,00023
Standard deviation	0,01923	0,01423	0,01120	0,01166
Kurtosis	20,29126	21,34550	16,67400	13,21810
Asymmetry	-1,42456	-1,64196	-1,72695	-0,06317
Jarque-Bera (p-value)	10160.06 (0,0000)	11447.81 (0,0000)	6572.24 (0,0000)	3376.42 (0,0000)
Panel B - Russia-Ukraine war (February 24, 2022 - May 05, 2023)				
Average	0,00042	0,00022	-0,000052	-0,000067
Standard deviation	0,01227	0,00992	0,00914	0,00803
Kurtosis	3,56139	4,89295	5,25942	6,84936
Asymmetry	0,03310	-0,35387	-0,60681	-0,86233
Jarque-Bera (p-value)	6.12 (0,0068)	50.03 (0,0000)	125.53 (0,0000)	214.24 (0,0000)

Source: Prepared by the author.

Figure 1 shows the daily returns of all emerging market stock indices for the periods of the Covid-19 pandemic (February 2020 - May 2023) and the Russia-Ukraine war (February 2022 - May 2023). The charts provide an overview of the high volatility during the current coronavirus and Russia-Ukraine war periods for all stock market indices in the four countries considered in the study. There is a clustering of volatility, meaning that the current period will have an impact on future periods of volatility, and all return series show a return to the mean, signifying stationarity.

Figure 1 - Stock market index returns

4.2 Stationarity and heteroscedasticity tests

To test whether a time series is stationary or not, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt and Shin (KPSS) tests with constant and trend are used. The results presented in Table 2 are statistically significant at the 5% level for the first difference, having verified stationarity.

Table 2 - Stationarity test

Stock market	Pandemic Covid-19		Russia-Ukraine war	
	ADF	KPSS	ADF	KPSS
Ibovespa (Brazil)	-34,5004	0,0449	-19,7834	0,0399
SENSEX (India)	-30,0724	0,0749	-17,4918	0,0563
Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia)	-25,6877	0,0774	-17,4265	0,0644
IDX composite (Indonesia)	-20,5581	0,0728	-17,9704	0,0256

Source: Prepared by the author on the basis of Eviews 10 results.

The ARCH-LM test was performed on the residuals of the return series. Thus, the ARCH-LM tests reveal that all the return series of the four emerging market stock indices have time-varying variances, and it can be seen in Table 3 that the test statistics are highly significant at the 1% error level. This guarantees the estimation based on the asymmetric GJR-GARCH model.

Table 3 - ARCH -LM test

Stock market	Pandemic Covid-19		Russia-Ukraine war	
	Statistic	P-value	Statistic	P-value
Ibovespa (Brazil)	25.7649	(0.0000)	36.6222	(0.0000)
SENSEX (India)	41.7286	(0.0000)	5.0552	(0.0002)
Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia)	50.3663	(0.0000)	14.8230	(0.0000)
IDX composite (Indonesia)	33.0240	(0.0000)	7.9602	(0.0000)

Source: Prepared by the author on the basis of Eviews 10 results.

Twenty-four models were calibrated using three types of distribution for the residuals: normal (Gaussian), student t and GED (Generalised error distribution) for emerging market indices.

The models highlighted in bold in Table 4 are those with the best forecasting results. An important feature of the analysis is that models that consider a conditional distribution other than normal (Gaussian) showed better results according to the AIC criterion (Akaike information criterion).

Table 4 - Distribution of the GJR -GARCH (1,1) model

Specifications	Ibovespa (Brazil)	SENSEX (India)	Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia)	IDX Composite (Indonesia)
Panel A - Pandemic Covid-19				
GJR-GARCH (1,1)				
Normal	-5,5917	-6,2539	-6,5894	-6,5670
Student t	-5,5998	-6,2784	-6,7046	-6,5216
GED	-5,5946	-6,2711	-6,6759	-6,5049
Panel B - Russia-Ukraine war				
GJR-GARCH (1,1)				
Normal	-5,9796	-6,5537	-6,7825	-6,8898
Student t	-5,9604	-6,5469	-6,7799	-6,9478
GED	-5,9579	-6,5470	-6,7785	-6,9114

Source: Prepared by the author on the basis of Eviews 10 results.

4.3 GJR-GARCH model results: COVID-19 pandemic

The GJR-GARCH (1,1) model was used to capture good (bad) news asymmetries in the stock markets of the emerging countries selected for this study during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In Table 5, the sum and is between 0.83309 for the Indonesian market and 0.90850 for the Brazilian market, verifying the stronger existence of ARCH and GARCH shocks in volatility, it is observed in the conditional variance of Ibovespa (Brazil), that volatility absorbs past events by at least 90.85% of the prior impact tracked in future movements.

The positive coefficients of the asymmetric effect (γ) are significant at the 1% level, demonstrating that negative shocks increase the volatility of emerging market stock indices more than positive shocks, i.e. that they had a leverage effect during the pandemic. The results show that negative shocks had a greater impact on conditional variance than good news.

This indicates that there are leverage effects on the stock markets of Brazil, India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia. The impact of the difference on the conditional variance can be determined between the ARCH effect and the leverage effect. In the Indian stock market, there is an impact of bad news on the conditional variance of 0.15; there is no impact of good news.

The ARCH-LM goodness-of-fit test indicators show that all adjusted models perform well and are statistically significant.

Table 5 - Results of the GJR-GARCH (1,1) model: Pandemic Covid -19

Specifications	Ibovespa (Brazil)	SENSEX (India)	Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia)	IDX Composite (Indonesia)
Conditional mean equation				
μ (constant)	0,000217 (0,6555)	0,001040 (0,0013)*	0,001223 (0,0000)*	0,000213 (0,5172)
Conditional variance equation				
ω (constant)	0,00000905 (0,0000)*	0,0000035 (0,0002)*	0,00000444 (0,0000)*	0,00000898 (0,0000)*
α_1 (ARCH effect)	0,0061 (0,0894)***	-0,03214 (0,0603)***	0,00604 (0,0335)**	0,06199 (0,0177)**
β_1 (GARCH effect)	0,9024 (0,0000)*	0,90096 (0,0000)*	0,83346 (0,0000)*	0,77110 (0,0000)*
γ (leverage)	0,0862 (0,0033)*	0,17737 (0,0000)*	0,18808 (0,0000)*	0,15236 (0,0000)*
$(\alpha_1 + \beta_1)$	0,90850	0,86882	0,83950	0,83309
Distribution error	<i>Student t</i>	<i>Student t</i>	<i>Student t</i>	<i>Normal</i>
Quality test				
ARCH-LM test (Estat F)	0,7752 (0,5677)**	0,14137 (0,9825)**	0,29293 (0,9169)**	0,03356 (0,9994)**

Note: p-value in parentheses. *significant at 1% level; ** significant at 5% level; *** significant at the 10% level.

Source: Prepared by the author on the basis of Eviews 10 results.

4.4 GJR-GARCH model results: Russia-Ukraine war

Table 6 shows that in the GJR-GARCH (1,1) model, the coefficients are statistically significant, indicating the presence of ARCH and GARCH effects.

The significant and positive value of the ARCH term (α_1) on the Brazilian market (Ibovespa) indicates that current volatility is affected by previous period volatility news and the presence of volatility clustering. The coefficients of the GARCH term (β_1) are high for all stock markets, indicating that current volatility or conditional variance is significantly affected by the conditional variance of the previous period.

The sum of the coefficients of the terms ($\alpha_1 + \beta_1$) is close to one for each emerging markets stock market index, verifying a high degree of volatility persistence, i.e. the current shocks to market returns triggered by the war may not disappear quickly, but rather persist for some time, given that the duration of the war is unknown.

The γ coefficient (leverage) revealed that stock market returns in Brazil, India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia are positive and significant at the 1% level, implying that bad news has a greater effect on the volatility of index returns during Russia's invasion of Ukraine.

The degree of impact of the difference on conditional variance can be observed from the ARCH effect and the leverage effect. The impact of bad news on the conditional variance of stock markets in India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia is 0.152, 0.208 and 0.126 respectively, and there is no impact of good news.

Table 6 - Results of the GJR-GARCH (1,1) model: Russia-Ukraine war

Specifications	Ibovespa (Brazil)	SENSEX (India)	Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia)	IDX Composite (Indonesia)
Conditional mean equation				
μ (constant)	0,000536 (0,3268)	0,000456 (0,3486)	0,000470 (0,0822)***	0,0000408 (0,9190)
Conditional variance equation				
ω (constant)	0,00000108 (0,0749)***	0,00000565 (0,0007)*	0,00000438 (0,0004)*	0,00000520 (0,0055)*
α_1 (ARCH effect)	0,00220 (0,0583)***	-0,04587 (0,0891)***	-0,03678 (0,0421)**	-0,11629 (0,0138)**
β_1 (GARCH effect)	0,96970 (0,0000)*	0,86711 (0,0000)*	0,84368 (0,0000)*	0,89260 (0,0000)*
γ (leverage)	0,03840 (0,0270)**	0,19805 (0,0000)*	0,24434 (0,0000)*	0,24181 (0,0022)*
$(\alpha_1 + \beta_1)$	0,97190)	0,82124	0,80690	0,77631
Distribution error	<i>Normal</i>	<i>Normal</i>	<i>Normal</i>	<i>Student t</i>
Quality test				
ARCH-LM test (Estat F)	0,82830 (0,5300)**	1,68990 (0,1371)**	1,14620 (0,3351)**	0,32416 (0,8983)**

Note: p-value in parentheses. *significant at 1% level; ** significant at 5% level;

*** significant at the 10% level.

Source: Prepared by the author on the basis of Eviews 10 results.

Figure 2 shows the dynamic patterns of estimated conditional volatility, measured in terms of conditional variances, in the selected emerging countries. As the figure shows, the COVID-19 pandemic led to a fall in stock prices, which in turn led to a massive increase in conditional volatilities on all the stock markets in the sample. The Brazilian stock market saw the highest peak in estimated volatility (0.0060), followed by India (0.0048), Saudi Arabia (0.0028) and Indonesia (0.0016) during the COVID-19 pandemic. These peaks are notably observed in March 2020.

The GJR-GARCH (1,1) model indicates that the significant increase in conditional volatility decreased over the COVID-19 period for all the stock markets analyzed. In other words, the shocks were absorbed by these markets and conditional volatility decreased.

During the conflict between Russia and Ukraine, Figure 2 shows that the IDX Composite (Indonesia recorded the highest average conditional variance (0.00053), followed by the SENSEX - India (0.00050) and the Athex Composite - Saudi Arabia (0.00042).

Figure 2 - Conditional volatility of emerging countries

4.5 Stock market leverage effect

For total leverage, Table 7 shows that the Brazilian stock market was most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, while the Indian, Saudi and Indonesian markets were most affected by Russia's invasion of Ukraine,

According to the results of the GJR-GARCH model (1,1), negative shocks caused by the war in Ukraine and the COVID-19 pandemic have a greater asymmetric effect on stock market volatility than positive shocks in two crisis events. If negative shocks increase by 1% due to the war, market volatility in India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia will increase by 0.19805%, 0.24434% and 0.24181% respectively.

Table 7 - Comparative event analysis: Leverage effect

Events/Stock market	Ibovespa (Brazil)	SENSEX (India)	Athex Composite (Saudi Arabia)	IDX Composite (Indonesia)
Pandemic Covid -19	0,08620	0,17737	0,18808	0,15236
War between Russia and Ukraine	0,03840	0,19805	0,24434	0,24181

Source: Prepared by the author.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines the effects of COVID-19 and the Russian-Ukrainian war on stock market volatility in the emerging markets of Brazil, India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia. Descriptive statistics show that standard deviation values were higher for all markets during the COVID-19 period than during the war. In addition, all markets showed high kurtosis during the pandemic. The study presented in this article analyzes the four selected emerging economies using the GJR-GARCH model.

The GARCH term coefficients are high for all stock markets during the COVID-19 pandemic, indicating long-term influences on stock market volatility. The Brazilian market (Ibovespa) has a higher GARCH effect than the other three markets (India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia). During the war between Russia and Ukraine, the Brazilian stock market showed a higher GARCH effect than the other three markets analyzed.

The sum of the coefficients of the $(\alpha + \beta)$ terms during crisis periods is close to one for each index, verifying a high degree of volatility persistence. The γ coefficient (leverage effect) revealed that stock market returns for the selected countries are positive and significant at the 1% level, implying that bad news has a greater effect than good news on the volatility of index returns during crisis periods.

In terms of total leverage, it was found that the Brazilian stock market was more affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, while the markets of India, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia were more affected by Russia invasion of Ukraine.

However, this model does not use macroeconomic variables such as GDP, interest rates, exchange rates, oil prices, etc. Future research should examine the performance of multivariate time series models using daily returns from international developed and emerging markets.

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